

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

BLOCKCHAIN IN EDUCATION: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to one of the ways of digitalization of education, which has not yet taken its rightful place - blockchain technology. It is concluded that in the context of globalization there is a significant transformation of the global educational process, which is associated with the introduction of information and communication technologies. Blockchain technology opens up fundamentally new opportunities for the education system, forms the conditions for the educational system to reach a qualitatively new level of development. The use of blockchain technology in the education system is associated with its ability to collect information, store it in an unchanged form, control the reliability of data, create rules and methods of management activities. The main directions of blockchain use in the digital transformation of education are described. However, new challenges to education from the "fourth industrial revolution" pose new, global challenges to the use of blockchain. This raises the problem of identifying and exploring new possibilities for the use of blockchain technology in education. The advantages of blockchain technology (distributed ledger) are described, which enable its use in the Global Education Space to solve new problems: the creation of common global educational services and resources, the collection of big data of the world countries on the implementation of SDGs, the unification of cross-country approaches to the implementation of the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap.

Keywords: education, blockchain technology, barriers to adoption, opportunities.

Introduction. At the beginning of the third millennium, the rapid development of information technologies has become part of the globalization process, one of the factors of significant transformations in the world educational process. Information and communication technologies have taken a significant place in the market of educational services. In recent years, record amounts of money have been invested in the EdTech market, - nearly \$20 billion in 2019 and more than \$16 billion in 2020 . However, the role of different IR-technologies in updating the content of education, dictated by environmental, socio-cultural and economic challenges of our time, as well as the achieved results, including the personal, intellectual, psycho-emotional development and health of students, is far from clear and has not been fully investigated so far. Following the euphoria of the opening possibilities of the transition to the information society, the time has come to deeply comprehend the new digital reality and to design a digital reality taking into account the strategic objectives of a society striving for sustainable development.

It is important that the processes of digitalization of education, including the rapid spread of distance learning, create long-term resources for the development of global and national education, overcome barriers to the introduction of educational technologies with proven safety, and stimulate the development of educational systems. According to experts, without adapting education informatization to the requirements of the "fourth industrial revolution", human civilization can expect even greater "information inequality" in society, deepening institutional problems associated with "information asymmetry".

Informatization of education is regarded as one of the most important strategic directions of civilization development. In this process, technologies such as

blockchain attract attention, making it possible to create common educational services and resources, control educational content and the quality of educational programs, and identify educational documents.

The article substantiates the possibilities of blockchain technology in the transformation of modern education.

Methods. The paper uses general scientific dialectical method of scientific knowledge, as well as special methods - comparative, statistical, system-structural, the method of generalization, etc.

The comparative method allowed to analyze the directions and conditions for the use of blockchain technology to solve the problems of education in individual countries to transfer the experience of using blockchain technology. The system-structural method was used in the process of identifying those areas of education, in which at present the most promising is the use of the technology under study. All these methods were applied in conjunction to achieve comprehensiveness, completeness and objectivity, specificity and validity of the conclusions.

The theoretical basis of the thesis work was the works of scientists in the field of informatization of education and the use of blockchain technology in this sphere of social activity.

Analysis of global startups that have attracted significant investments shows that the main investment areas are immersive technologies: virtual reality in education; use of artificial intelligence; robotics (robot kits that allow to learn STEM and form programming skills, Roybi products aimed at early language acquisition); educational services and various platforms; programs for content delivery and management of educational environment (learning environment); as well as blockchain technology

Attention to the problems of using blockchain technology in the educational system is associated with its ability to collect information, store it in an unchanged form, control the reliability of data, create rules and methods of management activity. In this regard, its use in the education system, according to researchers and practitioners, can significantly improve the quality of educational services not only at the country level, but also between countries, in the future - to facilitate the smooth exchange of information, technologies, teaching methods at the global level to implement, for example, the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development, Education for Global Citizenship, the promotion of education for sustainable development, the promotion of education for sustainable development, and the promotion of education for all. The use of blockchain technology in the educational process has been addressed in recent years by many researchers [1,4,5,6].

Scientists have identified promising areas of blockchain in education, the conditions for the introduction of blockchain technology in the education system, the risks associated with its use.

Meanwhile, contradictions have emerged,

- between the requirements that society places on the education system in terms of solving global problems, and the insufficiently studied possibilities for informatization of education to meet these requirements with the help of ICTs;

- between new challenges to ICT support for education in terms of online distance learning, and unpreparedness in terms of quality education using existing digital technologies;

- between the focus of education in the context of informatization on the already traditional technologies of digital learning and the apparent underestimation of the possibilities of using new technological solutions, such as blockchain technology;

- between the social order to improve the quality of management of educational organizations and the underestimation of the possibilities of using blockchain to solve these problems.

We explored the possibilities of using blockchain to solve educational problems in the context of globalization.

New challenges to education from the "Fourth Industrial Revolution" present new, global challenges to the use of blockchain. This raises the problem of identifying and exploring new possibilities for the use of blockchain technology in education.

Blockchain is a technology of collecting and storing information in a sequential chain of blocks with protection by means of cryptographic ciphers of its basic concepts, organizational principles of construction, architecture and classification of blockchain networks, blockchain proxy level. We compared and analyzed blockchain technologies based on Ethereum, EOS, Parity, Cosmos SDK. On the example of a number of universities and educational programs, we examined the method of issuing digital certificates and diplomas, the consensus mechanism, and the sharding method. And we drew a conclusion that the advantages

of blockchain technology (distributed register) in education are high level of transparency (distributed control over the network, transferred to users themselves), efficiency (high potential for fast and cheap transactions increases due to the removal of the need for intermediaries, third parties or a central controlling authority), security (thanks to an innovative information storage system in a distributed throughout the network database, such system is extremely difficult to break and data - to change. This makes it possible to use blockchain in the Global Education Space to solve new tasks: creation of common global educational services and resources, collection of big data of the world countries on the implementation of SDGs, unification of cross-country approaches to the implementation of the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap [6]. We have distinguished the phases of introduction of new technological solutions into the national education systems, which allows us to determine the place of the country in the technological segment of educational system development, which determines its overall quality.

On this basis, we have developed a scenario approach to the implementation of blockchain technology in the process of digitalization of education. We formulated the problem of modeling the scenario of creating a "digital profile of learners" based on the use of smart contracts method and the creation of smart contracts in the Ethereum network. Such a scenario is related to ensuring the sustainable development of the educational organization, the implementation of homeostatic model of management in it. It is indicative that blockchain technology implements homeostatic principles of management, providing the system with reliability of functioning, adaptability to changing conditions, protection from failures and self-regulation. All autonomous groups of blocks of the homeostatic management model are represented in blockchain technology (the blocks of the first group are the simulator of external environment impacts E on the management system of educational organization S; the blocks of the second group are the actual model of the homeostasis process of the management system S under study; the blocks of the third group serve for automated decision control in accordance with the stated rules as well as for fixation and processing of results of decisions made). Blockchain technology is able to provide an educational organization with the necessary level of sustainability through the transition to a management model that provides, on the one hand, the creation of a "decentralized autonomous organization" (Distributed Autonomous Organizations, DAO), on the other hand, a relatively universal management, based on a system of standards. We have developed an integrated model for the implementation of blockchain technology in the digital environment of the educational process based on the improvement of PBFT [7]. We propose a consensus mechanism (Boneh - Lynn - Shacham) that is linearly scalable in terms of communication complexity. This consensus uses an approach that differs from those previously discussed - with Proof of Share (PoS) as a validator registration mechanism or Sybil attack prevention mechanism. Such a method contains a main chain

and a Chardi set. The main chain serves as an identity registry, while the Shardi chains store individual blockchain states and simultaneously process transactions. This algorithm uses randomness generation by combining a random function checker (VRF) and a delay checker (VDF) and includes PoS in the sharding process, which shifts fragment protection issues from a minimum number of nodes to a minimum number of voting shares. Based on the research conducted, it is concluded that blockchain technology in education is a public good that ensures the development of the educational institution along the path of transparency, democracy, security, accessibility, sustainability, efficiency and inclusiveness, implementing the concept of "Education 4.0" [8].

What prevents blockchain implementation in education? The study of its prospects on the example of the educational systems of Eastern European countries has highlighted the typical problems that currently hinder their full participation in the global transformation. These are inactive marketing policy of education, lack of efficiency of distance learning and online education, lagging information infrastructure of universities, including the use of blockchain technology, lack of awareness of educational institutions and teachers about global trends in education development, the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development, Sustainable Development Goal 4. The latter circumstance is associated with the low level of scientific interest and technological support of blockchain technology in these countries (Fig. 1). Thus, if the number of patents in the field of blockchain technology with the U.S. 648, in Korea - 66, in Australia - 40, then, for example, in Russia - 2 (according to April 2020)

An analysis of the scientific literature allowed us to formulate a definition of blockchain in relation to the educational environment. First, it is a system for storing specific information related to the educational sphere, using a software module that implements an algorithm that processes the information content of ordered interconnected data blocks as a whole using cryptographic and data protection technologies to ensure and maintain the integrity of the Global Education Space. Such a system controls the passage of transactions performed by an educational organization, which can be considered a minimum amount of information transactions that make sense and are considered to be fully completed (e.g., certificate of education transactions). Second, blockchain technology provides a high level of security for data storage and transmission, an open and transparent network infrastructure, decentralization, and low operating costs.

This technology can already potentially be "embedded" in national education systems [2,9]:

- pedagogical management processes, in the development of educational programs and standardization of educational systems, in activities related to information protection and protection of students' personal data (for example, a student can check at any time which body or entity of educational activity had access to his/her electronic data, since any such access to personal data is documented and thus ensures transparency, security

and authenticity of use of information concerning students); if on a global

into unified document management systems, as well as into digital services of formation, use, storage of information and/or control over information used in the educational sphere, which ensures trust to electronic data and documents; if at the global level the problem of trust and security, confidentiality, identifiability will be solved

to a blockchain infrastructure focused on academic research and publications, which will allow to build an infrastructure that will automatically record data on new publications in the blockchain and store a constantly updated picture of the links between publications (references, citations), which will solve the problems of stratification of scientific publications by the impact factor of a particular publication, citation index, etc.

into educational disciplines dedicated to the use of blockchain technology, as well as massive open online courses, the popularity of which is constantly growing, as they provide the opportunity to obtain practical knowledge from anywhere in the world, as well as have a lower cost of training. Proceeding from the possibility of combining individual courses, forming separate blocks of courses, it becomes possible to synthesize different learning strategies for narrow specializations, at the same time, blockchain allows to standardize certificates and diplomas of universities and educational online portals, which will allow to legalize them for all participants of the Global Education Space.

Prospective directions of blockchain technology implementation in the development of the Global Education Space were considered.

It is an increase of pedagogical staff readiness to use digital technologies. Replacing outdated computer equipment (especially in rural schools). Provision of a stable working Internet in remote areas. Overcoming psychological problems of blockchain use, which in the minds of many people is firmly associated with cryptocurrency and the shadow market. Overcoming teachers' cautious attitude to global processes as a risk of losing national advantages of education, etc.

Consideration of the possibilities of blockchain in education shows that at the beginning of the XXI century the global educational system is at a turning point of development. Future forms, paradigms and models of education will be influenced by the evolution of civilization, and education as its important global component should promote those forms of development that will implement the strategy of human survival and biosphere preservation to the greatest extent. It is the information component that is the fundamental basis for the implementation of the Global Action Program on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for the implementation of this program.

We have highlighted four applications of blockchain [2,3]. A generalizing and advisory one - collecting examples of best practices reflecting the implementation of the Global Action Agenda on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for its implementation, as well as institutional-wide approaches

used at the government, public and private sector, and education levels aimed at its implementation.

Programmatic and substantive - creation of global information platforms where best practices in the implementation of the Global Action Program on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for the implementation of the Program and institution-wide approaches can be uploaded.

Regulatory - to develop a practical guide in the form of a checklist showing how to implement the Global Action Agenda on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for implementing the Agenda through a whole-institution approach. The guide will include specific questions to facilitate reflection on a whole-institution approach at the institutional, governmental, educational, and organizational levels.

Controlling - development of accreditation conditions and a set of quality criteria for the implementation of the Global Action Program on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for the implementation of this program to monitor its implementation. Blockchain technology is used for operations with personal data, replenished personally for a particular child by teachers and specialists, constitute information for the work of supervisory groups. Blockchain is needed to check the portfolios and certification of teachers and specialists who are invited to work, to track the dynamics of their professional development. Blockchain is indispensable for creating a common data bank of professional literature for teachers and specialists in the field of inclusion, including the possibility of professional advice for school staff in difficult situations. The creation of the system "Control of educational programs for the possibility of their use in inclusion classes" based on the use of blockchain technology seems promising. The introduction of blockchain in the system of control of educational programs for their possible use in inclusion classes will allow:

- reliably, online, identify needs for improving existing educational programs and developing new programs adapted for use in inclusion classrooms;
- develop "passports of educational programs" in accordance with the requirements of the program passing through the blockchain system;
- monitor in real time (smart contract algorithm) the compliance with the formulated requirements at all stages of the educational program implementation;
- maintain a unified electronic document flow (reporting on the state of the educational process, passports of educational programs, reports on the state of health and learning achievements of students in the inclusion classes, etc.) [3].

As a result, it is concluded that blockchain technology is an indispensable tool for the development of modern education system, given its globalization, the

dialectic of national and global, the desire for informatization and informational openness. The level of digitalization of education and its quality is directly related to the active implementation of "breakthrough technologies" that can bring the educational system to a new level of development, in particular with the introduction of blockchain technology in the educational system.

References:

1. Arishi, H.A.; Mavaluru, D.; Mythily, R. (2018). Block chain technology and its applications for virtual education. *J. Adv. Res. Dyn. Control Syst.* 10, pp. 1780–1785.
2. Dziatkovskii A. and Hryneuski U. (2021) Researching the Usage of Blockchain in Higher Education // 1st International Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning in Higher Education (TELE), 2021, pp. 133-138, doi: 10.1109/TELE52840.2021.9482482. (Scopus) - <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/9482410/proceeding>
3. Dziatkovskii A. Education through the lens of blockchain and vice versa // *Journal of Modern Education Review* (ISSN 2155-7993, USA), Academic Star Publishing Company, 2021, Issue 6.
4. Filvà, D.A., García-Peñalvo, F.J., Forment, M.A., Escudero, D.F., Casañ, M.J. (2018). Privacy and identity management in Learning Analytics processes with Blockchain. In: *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality - TEEM'18*. pp. 997–1003. ACM Press, New York, USA.
5. Ghaffar, A. and Hussain, M. (2019). BCEAP-A blockchain embedded academic paradigm to augment legacy education through application. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems*, №45, pp. 1–11.
6. Grech, A., & Camilleri, A. F. (2017). Blockchain in education. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. URL: https://www.pedocs.de/volltexte/2018/15013/pdf/Grech_Camilleri_2017;Blockchain_in_Education.pdf.
7. Mathews, M. (2019). The blockchain movement in education. The Tambellini Group Blog, URL: <https://www.thetambellini.com/the-blockchain-movement-in-education/>.
8. Raimund, R. and Rosário, A. (2021). Blockchain System in the Higher Education. *Eur. J. Investig. Health Psychol. Educ.* № 11, pp. 276-294.
9. Roebuck, K. (2019). Five ways blockchain is revolutionizing higher education. *Forbes' Oracle Sponsored Blog*, URL: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/oracle/2019/01/02/5-ways-blockchain-is-revolutionizing-higher-education/#677515497c41>.